

Comparative Performance Evaluation of Small Cap Mutual Funds : Direct and Regular Schemes

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Abstract : *In this paper, the Performance of thirteen open-ended, equity small cap schemes related to thirteen private sector mutual funds are evaluated. The period of the study covers the period from 1st April 2016 to 31st March 2022. To evaluate the performance of the selected mutual fund schemes, monthly returns are compared with Benchmark- S&P BSE Small Cap Index return. Risk Free Rate has been taken as average fixed deposit rate of State bank of India. Further, various statistical tools like average, standard deviation, coefficient of determination, beta and the risk adjusted performance measures suggested by Sharpe (1966), Jenson (1968), and Treynor (1965) are employed to evaluate the performance for the above selected period.*

Keywords : S&P BSE Small Cap Index, Small Cap Mutual Funds, Open-ended, Growth Option.

Introduction

Mutual Funds works on the principle of Do not put all eggs in one basket i.e. Diversification. Diversification is a device that reduces the risk because all stocks have different degree of risk i. e. they may not move in the same direction in the same proportion at the same time. Mutual funds provide opportunities for small and medium investors to participate in the capital market without assuming a very high degree of risk. Mutual fund issues units to the investors in accordance with amount of money invested by them. Investors of mutual funds are known as unit holders. The profits or losses are shared by the investors in proportion to their investment in that mutual fund. The mutual funds normally offer a number of schemes with different investment objectives which are launched from time to time.

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Review of Literature

Mutual fund industry in India began in 1963 with the formation of Unit trust of India (UTI) and the existing of a mutual fund industry in India is for over more than 55 years, there have been only a few studies, which examined the performance of Indian mutual funds using standard methodology for Mid cap funds. a brief review of these studies is now presented below:

Sarkar [1992] critically examined mutual fund performance evaluation methodology. He opined that both Sharpe [1966] and Treynor [1965] performance measures rank mutual funds' performance in similar fashion though they differ in the measurement of risk parameter.

Shome [1994] reported that average rate of return of selected Indian mutual funds was marginally lower than that of the benchmark portfolio (BSE Sensex). However, he reported that the risk measure of the majority of funds was higher than that of the benchmark portfolio. This implies that the fund managers were taking larger risk but were generating lower returns.

Kale and Uma [1995] evaluated the performance of 77 mutual fund schemes managed by eight mutual funds. The rates of return were compared with the return of the BSE National Index over the sample period to evaluate the performance of the scheme with the market. The study also examined the accounting and disclosure policies followed by the above mutual funds.

Sahadevan and Raju [1996] have carried out their study on mutual funds. Their study has focus on data presentation on expenses and other related aspects, which were generally covered in annual reports of the mutual funds.

Sadhak [1997] tried to trace the historical background of mutual fund industry. It has presented accurately the marketing and investment strategies followed by mutual fund houses of India. It contained statistical information about growth of mutual fund industry in terms of funds available for investment and investors' number of accounts holding.

Jayadev M [1998] evaluated the performance of 62 mutual funds schemes using monthly NAV data for varying period 1987-1995. He reported superior performance for a large mass (30 out of 44) of the sample schemes when total risk was considered. However, in terms of systematic risk only 24 out of 44 schemes outperformed the benchmark portfolio. He also found that some of the Indian Mutual funds were not diversified properly.

Gupta and Sehgal [2000] has wider and comprehensive view. They evaluated investment performance of 80 mutual fund schemes of the Indian mutual fund market over the period 1992-96. In addition, they tested several related propositions regarding fund diversification, consistency of performance, parameter stationary over time, performance in relation to fund objectives and risk-return relationship and reported that mutual fund industry had performed reasonably well during the study period. However, there is a lack of adequate diversification. They also found evidence to support consistency of performance. Finally, a significant and positive risk return relationship was measured by the study when standard deviation was used a basis for risk measurement.

Mishra [2001] evaluated performance for the period from April 1992 to December 1996. The sample size was 24 public sector sponsored mutual funds. The performance was evaluated in terms of rate of return, , Sharpe, Treynor and Jensen's measures of performance. The study also considered beta's instability issues. Conclusion of the study was uncheerful performance of PSU mutual funds in India, in general.

Singh and Singh have highlighted the facts that mutual funds in India have not attained equal status as their counterparts in other developed countries. The study emphasized on the gradual and slow growth of mutual funds industry in India by giving an exclusive attention to the UTI as it was through to be the pioneers in the field of mutual funds in India. The offshore mutual funds, private mutual funds, money market funds, has been critically analyzed in this study.

Vikas Kumar [2010] Evaluated the performance of 20 mutual funds schemes managed by five mutual funds using monthly NAV for 10 year i.e. 120 months for the period from 1st Jan 2000 to 31st Dec 2009. The rate of return was compared with the BSE National 100 index over the above period. The performance was evaluated in the terms of rate of return, systematic risk (i.e. Beta), Total risk (i.e. S.D.), coefficient of determination and risk adjusted performance suggested by Treynor (1965), Sharpe (1966) and Jensen (1968). The outcome shows that out of 20 schemes selected equity schemes shows better return as compared to debt and balanced schemes.

Shanmugham and Zabiulla (2011) : addressed the financial performance of mutual funds in the framework of risk and return dimensions. In order to measure financial performance of selected thirty mutual fund schemes investment performance measures, cluster analysis and correlation analysis are

used covering the period of forty-five months that span from April 2006 to December 2009. They concluded that Reliance diversified power fund performed better in terms of providing returns to the investors, eight of the sample funds were considered to be riskier as evidenced by their highest estimate of standard deviation and the sample mutual fund schemes are less volatile than the market portfolio.

Iqbal (2012) : made a comparative study of private sector mutual funds and public sector mutual funds to check whether private sector mutual funds are performing better and providing better results to investors or public sector mutual funds in India. He concluded with the help of empirical data that the private sector mutual fund Companies have shown very impressive growth in comparison to public sector mutual fund companies and it can be said that the private sector mutual funds have performed better and given good results with better NAV to the investors.

Joshi (2016) : tried to identify the important factors which motivate the small investors in Nagpur city of India who invest in Equity and equity linked saving schemes (ELSS) of mutual fund in terms of factors which discriminates between such investors and non-investors using Logistic Regression Model. He concluded that amongst the various factors motivating investors to invest in mutual funds, the returns on investment and lock in period are the two significant factors; amongst the various sources of information for the respondents, the internet and friends/relatives are the two significant factors and amongst the major factors hindering investment in mutual funds, high risk and inefficient investment advisors are the significant factors influencing the decision making of the investors in mutual fund which discriminates between investors and non-investors in mutual fund.

Reepu (2017) : attempted to know about Mutual Fund, its various schemes and analyse the different risk factors involved. He discussed that diversification and SIP allows investor to manage the risks, moreover, with the investment in mutual fund the investor can avail tax benefits too. Sponsor, trust, trustee, transfer agent, asset management company etc. forms key element of mutual fund structure.

Levi and Garag (2017) : performed comparative study of thirteen large cap and mid cap regular equity mutual fund, SIP and nifty index returns. The findings showed that mean returns of large cap regular equity mutual fund exceeded nifty index returns and the same thing held good for mid cap funds as well. SIP returns lay somewhere between regular mutual funds and nifty index returns.

From the multiple comparison tables, it is concluded that there were no significant differences between nifty index return and regular mutual fund return in addition to nifty index return and SIP return respectively.

Agarwal and Mirza (2017) : assessed the performance of Indian mutual fund schemes using Sharpe ratio, Treynor ratio, Jensen's Alpha and Value at Risk for a sample of 100 Indian mutual fund schemes for the period from January 2013 to June 2016. The sample comprises of 18 diversified equity schemes, 9 tax saving schemes, 17 large cap funds, 16 long term gilt, 8 long term income, 8 short term income funds, 11 small/mid cap funds and 12 ultra-short-term funds. They concluded that results of Sharpe ratio and Treynor ratio reflect that 90 percent of the schemes have performed better than their benchmarks which reflect that during the above study period selected funds' schemes have done fairly well and have outperformed the market.

Research Gap

In the above literature no studies have made an attempt to make a comparative analysis of Mutual fund returns of small cap funds using Benchmarks i.e., S&P BSE Small cap Index and also the Risk-free rate taken as average Interest rate of fixed deposit rate of state bank of India during the selected period of this study. In India retail investors hardly understand the performance measures tools like Sharpe, Treynor, Jensen models. Still very few studies have made an attempt to calculate the return on mutual funds which can be easily understandable by the retail investors.

Significance of the Study

The need for evaluating the performance of mutual fund schemes in India especially small cap funds to see whether the small cap mutual fund schemes are outperforming or underperforming than the benchmark and to see the competency of schemes to make out a strong case for investment. The present paper investigates the performance of open-ended, growth-oriented equity, small cap schemes. It enables an investor to access as to how much return has been generated by the portfolio manager and what risk level has been assumed in generating such returns. This study is expected to fill this gap. The present research work is expected to be useful especially to managers of mutual funds, academicians, present and future research scholars, present and potential investors, and also government and regulated bodies. This study shall guide the investors in planning and effecting their decisions regarding investments in

mutual funds. It will also act as a guide for new investors who is willing to invest in small cap mutual fund.

Objectives of the Study

- To evaluate the performance of sample small cap schemes.
- To compare schemes', return and risk with benchmark i.e. S&P BSE Small cap Index.
- To appraise the performance of mutual funds with regard to risk-return adjustment, the model suggested by Sharpe, Treynor and Jensen.

Limitations of the Study

For the purpose of performance evaluation, those schemes have been selected which are in operation during 6 years i.e. 1st April 2016 to 31st March 2022. Only open-ended, growth option equity schemes of Private Sector Mutual Funds have been considered for this purpose. Performance evaluation of all schemes is not possible due to unavailability of data.

Scope for Further Research

As evaluating the performance of Mutual Fund is an ongoing process and a never-ending task. This study has taken only open-ended schemes for its consideration and thus, a similar study can be done on Close-ended schemes. As in the present study an attempt has been made to compare the selected small cap schemes with one benchmark i.e. S&P BSE Small cap Index, so same can be made with various other benchmarks and different Risk-free returns which is taken as fixed deposit rate of state bank of India in the present study. For further research overall compare of small cap, mid cap and large cap mutual funds with short and long run point of view.

Research Methodology

Benchmark Index

For this study, S&P BSE Small cap Index has been used as a proxy for market index. Hence it would cover the majority percentage of different scheme portfolios and therefore is expected to provide better performance benchmark.

Risk Free Rate

Risk free rate of return refers to that minimum return on investment that has no risk of losing the amount of investment over which it is earned. In this present study, it has been taken as Deposit rate of banks on the average rate from April-1, 2016 to March-31, 2022 marked as 0.005167 per month.

Period of Study

The growth-oriented schemes, which have been floated by the Private Sector Mutual Funds during the period 1st April, 2016 to 31st March, 2022 are considered for the purpose of the study. Monthly Net Asset Value (NAV) as declared by the relevant mutual funds during the above period has been used for this purpose.

Data

Study examines thirteen open-ended equity schemes (Direct Scheme) and thirteen open-ended equity schemes (Regular Scheme) with growth option being launched by Private Sector Mutual Funds. These schemes have been selected on the basis of regular data availability during the period of 1st April 2016 to 31st March 202\2. Monthly Net Asset Value (NAV) data have been used of the above period. NAV for the study is collected from AMFI (Association of Mutual Funds in India) and selected mutual funds' websites.

Statistical Tools

For the purpose of the performance evaluation various tools are used to measure the performance which are as Average Return, Standard Deviation, Beta, Sharpe, Treynor and Jensen.

Direct Scheme

Direct scheme is a scheme in which money is invested in mutual fund company directly by investors using mutual fund own website or application.

Regular Scheme

Regular scheme is a scheme in which money is invested in mutual fund company through broker.

Analysis and Interpretation

Table-1 : List of Sample Mutual Funds Schemes

Name of the Equity Scheme Selected
Aditya Birla Sunlife Small Cap Fund
Axis Small Cap Fund
DSP Small Cap Fund
Franklin Templeton Mutual Fund
HDFC Small Cap Fund
ICICI Prudential Small Cap Fund
Kotak Small Cap Fund
L & T Emerging Business Fund
Nippon India Small Cap Fund
Quant Small Cap Fund
SBI Small Cap Fund
Sundaram Small Cap Fund
Union Small Cap Fund

Table-2 shows the average return earned by the various schemes. For calculation of average return earned by the schemes Growth in the value for each month over the previous month has been divided by the value of the previous month. Then the average of the full series has been taken.

Direct Scheme

In the sample schemes selected for the study, it is observed that Ten out of Thirteen schemes had shown the better return as compared to **S&P BSE Small Cap Index** (0.016325). **Nippon India Small Cap fund** (0.021082) has outperformed all the other sample schemes and the benchmarks, followed by **SBI Small Cap fund** (0.019488) and **L&T Emerging Business fund** (0.019418). **Aditya Birla Sunlife Small Cap Fund** (0.013916) has shown the worst performance in the sample schemes.

Regular Scheme

In the sample schemes selected for the study, it is observed that seven out of thirteen schemes had shown the better return as compared to **S&P BSE Small Cap Index** (0.016325). **Nippon India Small Cap fund** (0.019966) has outperformed all the other sample schemes and the benchmarks, followed by **L&T Emerging Business fund** (0.018585) and **SBI Small Cap fund** (0.018533). **Aditya Birla Sunlife Small Cap Fund** (0.013239) has shown the worst performance in the sample schemes.

Table-2 : Average Monthly Return Earned by the Schemes

Schemes	Average Return	
	Direct Scheme	Regular Scheme
Aditya Birla Sunlife Small Cap Fund	0.013916	0.013239
Axis Small Cap Fund	0.019175	0.015640
DSP Small Cap Fund	0.016769	0.016162
Franklin India Smaller Companies Fund	0.014692	0.013801
HDFC Small Cap Fund	0.017723	0.016739
ICICI Prudential Small Cap Fund	0.017326	0.016477
Kotak Small Cap Fund	0.019411	0.018309
L & T Emerging Business Fund	0.019418	0.018585
Nippon India Small Cap Fund	0.021082	0.019966
Quant Small Cap Fund	0.017812	0.017272
SBI Small Cap Fund	0.019488	0.018533
Sundaram Small Cap Fund	0.015097	0.014383
Union S.mall Cap Fund	0.017811	0.015272

Source : Compiled by the Authors.

Table-3 shows the standard deviation of selected schemes. It is the most common expression to measure risk of the fund return. Higher the value of standard deviation of the fund returns, greater will be the total risk carried by the fund.

Direct Scheme

It is observed that the maximum deviation of funds return is shown by **Union Small Cap Fund** (0.090226) followed by **Sundaram Small Cap Fund** (0.072282) and **Nippon Small Cap fund** (0.071329) whereas **Axis Small Cap Fund** (0.055294) was least risky scheme with lowest standard deviation on the other hand Standard Deviation of benchmark S&P BSE Small Cap Index is (0.069687). It could be seen here that ten out of thirteen schemes selected for study shows less standard deviation then S&P BSE Small Cap Index.

Regular Scheme

It is observed that the maximum deviation of funds return is shown by **Sundaram Small Cap Fund** (0.072456) followed by **Aditya Birla Sunlife Small Cap fund** (0.069715) and **Quant Small Cap Fund** (0.068348) whereas **Axis Small Cap Fund** (0.054496) was least risky scheme with lowest standard deviation on the other hand Standard Deviation of benchmark S&P BSE Small Cap Index is (0.069687). It could be seen here that Eleven out of thirteen schemes selected for study shows less standard deviation than S&P BSE Small Cap Index.

Table-3 : Results of Standard Deviation of Select Small Cap Funds

Schemes	Standard Deviation	
	Direct Scheme	Regular Scheme
Aditya Birla Sunlife Small Cap Fund	0.069632	0.069715
Axis Small Cap Fund	0.055294	0.054496
DSP Small Cap Fund	0.066398	0.066331
Franklin India Smaller Companies Fund	0.061766	0.061654
HDFC Small Cap Fund	0.065601	0.065555
ICICI Prudential Small Cap Fund	0.068021	0.067949
Kotak Small Cap Fund	0.064415	0.066006
L & T Emerging Business Fund	0.065043	0.065007
Nippon India Small Cap Fund	0.071329	0.067733
Quant Small Cap Fund	0.068592	0.068348
SBI Small Cap Fund	0.061104	0.061195
Sundaram Small Cap Fund	0.072282	0.072456
Union Small Cap Fund	0.090261	0.061211

Source : Compiled by the Authors.

Risk - Return Classification of Sample Schemes

In order to undertake further analysis, sample schemes have been classified into the following four categories on the basis of their return and risk characteristics:

- 1) **High Return and High Risk** : This category includes all those schemes whose returns as well as standard deviations are higher than that of the market.
- 2) **High Return and Low Risk** : This category comprises those schemes whose returns are more than the market but their standard deviations are lower than that of the market.
- 3) **Low Return and Low Risk** : This category consists of schemes whose average returns are less than the average market return and their standard deviations are also lower than that of the market.
- 4) **Low return and High Risk** : The final category includes all those schemes whose returns have been found to be lower than that of the market but their standard deviations are higher than that of the market.

Categorizations of Schemes

Table 1.4 presents the risk return grid of Mutual Funds schemes

Direct Scheme

After classification of the sample schemes into risk return category

- 02 scheme falls in category 1st i.e. **High Return High Risk**
- Further 08 schemes fall in 2nd category i.e. **High return and low risk**. These 10 schemes fulfil one basic objective of Mutual Fund i.e. High Return and Low Risk compared to the capital market.
- Next 02 schemes fall in 3rd category i.e. **Low Return and Low Risk**, and also,
- 01 scheme falls in 4th category i.e. **Low Return and High Risk**.

Table-4 (a) : Risk Return Grid of Mutual Funds Scheme (Direct Schemes) compared to S&P BSE Small Cap Index

<p style="text-align: center;"><u>Category-1</u></p> <p style="text-align: center;">HIGH RETURN, HIGH RISK</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Union Small Cap Fund Nippon India Small Cap Fund</p>	<p style="text-align: center;"><u>Category-2</u></p> <p style="text-align: center;">HIGH RETURN, LOW RISK</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Axis Small Cap Fund DSP Small Cap Fund HDFC Small Cap Fund ICICI Prudential Small Cap Fund Kotak Small Cap Fund L&T Emerging Business Fund Quant Small Cap Fund SBI Small Cap Fund</p>
<p style="text-align: center;"><u>Category-3</u></p> <p style="text-align: center;">LOW RETURN, LOW RISK</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Aditya Birla Sunlife Small Cap Fund Franklin India Smaller Companies Fund</p>	<p style="text-align: center;"><u>Category-4</u></p> <p style="text-align: center;">LOW RETURN, HIGH RISK</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Sundaram Small Cap Fund</p>

Source : Compiled by the Author.

Regular Scheme

After classification of the sample schemes into risk return category

- **No scheme** falls in category 1st i.e. **High Return High Risk**
- Further **07 schemes** fall in 2nd category i.e. **High return and low risk**. These 09 schemes fulfil one basic objective of Mutual Fund i.e. High Return and Low Risk compared to the capital market.
- Next **04 schemes** fall in 3rd category i.e. **Low Return and Low Risk**, and also,
- **02 scheme** falls in 4th category i.e. **Low Return and High Risk**.

Table- 1.4 (b) : Risk Return Grid of Mutual Funds Schemes (Regular Scheme) Compared to S&P BSE Small Cap Index

<p style="text-align: center;">Category-1 HIGH RETURN, HIGH RISK No Scheme</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Category-2 HIGH RETURN, LOW RISK HDFC Small Cap Fund ICICI Prudential Small Cap Fund Kotak Small Cap Fund L&T Emerging Business Fund Nippon India Small Cap Fund Quant Small Cap Fund SBI Small Cap Fund</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Category-3 LOW RETURN, LOW RISK Axis Small Cap Fund DSP Small Cap Fund Franklin India Smaller Companies Fund Union Small Cap Fund</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Category-4 LOW RETURN, HIGH RISK Aditya Birla Sunlife Small Cap Fund Sundaram Small Cap Fund</p>

Source : Compiled by the Author.

Direct Scheme

Table 1.5 presents the systematic risk of the sample schemes. Considered for the purpose of this study all of the schemes have beta less than 1 (i.e. market beta) implying thereby that all these schemes selected for the study hold portfolios that were less risky than the market portfolio. The best beta value was shown by **Quant Small Cap Fund** (0.743892) and the worst was shown by **Sundaram Small Cap Fund** (1.006305).

Regular Scheme

Table-5 presents the systematic risk of the sample schemes. Considered for the purpose of this study all of the schemes have beta less than 1 (i.e. market beta) implying thereby that all these schemes selected for the study hold portfolios that were less risky than the market portfolio. The best beta value

was shown by **Axis Small Cap Fund** (0.691795) and the worst was shown by **Sundaram Small Cap Fund** (1.019505).

Table-5 : Results of BETA of Select Small Cap Funds

Schemes	BETA	
	Direct Scheme	Regular Scheme
Aditya Birla Sunlife Small Cap Fund	0.969514	0.971840
Axis Small Cap Fund	0.747334	0.691794
DSP Small Cap Fund	0.929621	0.928842
Franklin India Smaller Companies Fund	0.849716	0.849784
HDFC Small Cap Fund	0.912879	0.912440
ICICI Prudential Small Cap Fund	0.920463	0.919953
Kotak Small Cap Fund	0.892126	0.904676
L & T Emerging Business Fund	0.909751	0.909066
Nippon India Small Cap Fund	0.974936	0.958485
Quant Small Cap Fund	0.743892	0.742112
SBI Small Cap Fund	0.835490	0.836139
Sundaram Small Cap Fund	1.006305	1.019505
Union Small Cap Fund	0.795011	0.845632

Source : Compiled by the Author.

Direct Scheme

Table-6 depicts value of Sharpe's reward to variability ratio. It is an excess return earned over risk free return per unit of risk involved, i.e. per unit of standard deviation. Positive value of the index shows good performance it could be seen that 09 sample schemes have recorded better Sharpe index and 04 sample schemes have recorded lower Sharp index than the S&P BSE Small Cap Index (0.160117). **Aditya Birla Sunlife Small Cap Fund** have shown the worst sharp ratio (0.125645) and **Axis Small Cap Fund** (0.253341) have shown the best Sharpe ratio among the selected schemes. This indicates Nearly 69 percent schemes have outperformed the S&P BSE Small Cap index. This implies that the funds decision for diversified portfolio in a falling market has proved successful to some extent in earning higher excess returns per unit of risk as compared to the market.

Regular Scheme

Table-6 depicts value of Sharpe's reward to variability ratio. It is an excess return earned over risk free return per unit of risk involved, i.e. per unit of standard deviation. Positive value of the index shows good performance it could be seen that 07 sample schemes have recorded better Sharpe index and 06 sample schemes have recorded lower Sharpe index than the S&P BSE Small Cap Index (0.160117). **Aditya Birla Sunlife Small Cap Fund** have shown the worst sharp ratio (0.115795) and **Nippon India Small Cap Fund** (0.218500) have shown the best Sharpe ratio among the selected schemes. This indicates Nearly 77 percent schemes have outperformed the S&P BSE Small Cap index. This implies that the funds decision for diversified portfolio in a falling market has proved successful to some extent in earning higher excess returns per unit of risk as compared to the market. The Sharpe index is important from small investor point of view who seek diversification through mutual funds, i.e. mutual funds are supposed to protect small investors against vagaries of stock markets and the fund managers of these schemes has done well to protect them.

Table-6 : Sharpe of the Schemes

Schemes	Sharpe	
	Direct Scheme	Regular Scheme
Aditya Birla Sunlife Small Cap Fund	0.0125645	0.115795
Axis Small Cap Fund	0.253341	0.132191
DSP Small Cap Fund	0.174739	0.165770
Franklin India Smaller Companies Fund	0.154223	0.140049
HDFC Small Cap Fund	0.191399	0.176532
ICICI Prudential Small Cap Fund	0.178760	0.166461
Kotak Small Cap Fund	0.221132	0.199104
L & T Emerging Business Fund	0.219112	0.206412
Nippon India Small Cap Fund	0.223126	0.218500
Quant Small Cap Fund	0.184358	0.177108
SBI Small Cap Fund	0.234374	0.218420
Sundaram Small Cap Fund	0.137386	0.127198
Union Small Cap Fund	0.140088	0.165097

Source : Compiled by the Author.

Direct Scheme

Table-7 shows Treynor of the scheme, it is the excess return over risk free return per unit of systematic risk i.e. beta. Here, all the schemes recorded positive value indicating thereby that the schemes provided adequate returns as against the level of risk involved in the investment. **Axis Small Cap Fund** (0.018744) shows the best Treynor ratio among all the selected schemes followed by **SBI Small Cap Fund** (0.017141) and **Quant Small Cap Fund** (0.016999) whereas **Aditya Birla Sunlife Small Cap Fund** (0.009024) has shown the worst performance. A higher Treynor Index as compared to market indicates that investor who invested in mutual fund to form well diversified portfolio did receive adequate return per unit of systematic risk undertaken.

Regular Scheme

Table-7 shows Treynor of the scheme, it is the excess return over risk free return per unit of systematic risk i.e. beta. Here, all the schemes recorded positive value indicating thereby that the schemes provided adequate returns as against the level of risk involved in the investment. **Quant Small Cap Fund** (0.016311) shows the best Treynor ratio among all the selected schemes followed by **SBI Small Cap Fund** (0.015986) and **Nippon India Small Cap Fund** (0.015441) whereas **Aditya Birla Sunlife Small Cap Fund** (0.008307) has shown the worst performance. A higher Treynor Index as compared to market indicates that investor who invested in mutual fund to form well diversified portfolio did receive adequate return per unit of systematic risk undertaken.

Table-7 : Treynor of the Schemes

Schemes	TREYNOR	
	Direct Scheme	Regular Scheme
Aditya Birla Sunlife Small Cap Fund	0.009024	0.008307
Axis Small Cap Fund	0.018744	0.015140
DSP Small Cap Fund	0.012481	0.011838
Franklin India Smaller Companies Fund	0.011211	0.010161
HDFC Small Cap Fund	0.013754	0.012683
ICICI Prudential Small Cap Fund	0.013210	0.012295

(Contd...)

Kotak Small Cap Fund	0.015967	0.014527
L & T Emerging Business Fund	0.015665	0.014760
Nippon India Small Cap Fund	0.016325	0.015441
Quant Small Cap Fund	0.016999	0.016311
SBI Small Cap Fund	0.017141	0.015986
Sundaram Small Cap Fund	0.009868	0.009040
Union Small Cap Fund	0.015905	0.011951

Source : Compiled by the Author.

Direct Scheme

Table-8 shows the Jensen's measures. It is the regression of excess return of the schemes with excess return of the market, acting as dependent and independent variables respectively. Higher positive value of alpha posted by the schemes indicates its better performance. The analysis of the table reveals that 11 schemes have positive Jensen's Measures and 02 schemes have negative value. Highest value of Jensen's Measure is shown in **Axis Small Cap Fund** (0.005669) followed by **Nippon India Small Cap Fund** (0.005037) and **SBI Small Cap Fund** (0.004999). Lowest Jensen's measure found in the case of **Aditya Birla Sunlife Small Cap Fund** (-0.002069). Higher value of Jensen's measures indicates good market timing ability of fund managers as regard investment in the securities.

Regular Scheme

Table-8 shows the Jensen's measures. It is the regression of excess return of the schemes with excess return of the market, acting as dependent and independent variables respectively. Higher positive value of alpha posted by the schemes indicates its better performance. The analysis of the table reveals that 10 schemes have positive Jensen's Measures and 03 schemes have negative value. Highest value of Jensen's Measure is shown in **Nippon India Small Cap Fund** (0.004105) followed by **SBI Small Cap Fund** (0.004037) and **Quant Small Cap Fund** (0.003824). Lowest Jensen's measure found again in the case of **Aditya Birla Sunlife Small Cap Fund** (-0.002771). Higher value of Jensen's measures indicates good market timing ability of fund managers as regard investment in the securities.

Table-8 : Results of Jenson on Select Small Cap Funds

Schemes	JENSON	
	Direct Scheme	Regular Scheme
Aditya Birla Sunlife Small Cap Fund	-0.002069	-0.002771
Axis Small Cap Fund	0.005669	0.002755
DSP Small Cap Fund	0.001230	0.000632
Franklin India Small Cap Fund	0.000045	-0.000847
HDFC Small Cap Fund	0.002370	0.001392
ICICI Prudential Small Cap Fund	0.001889	0.001046
Kotak Small Cap Fund	0.004290	0.003048
L & T Emerging Business Fund	0.004101	0.003275
Nippon India Small Cap Fund	0.005037	0.004105
Quant Small Cap Fund	0.004345	0.003824
SBI Small Cap Fund	0.004999	0.004037
Sundaram Small Cap Fund	-0.001298	-0.002159
Union Small Cap Fund	0.003774	0.000670

Source : Compiled by the Author.

Table-9 shows the ranking of the scheme according to Average Return and Standard Deviation where the scheme with the highest value is ranked 1 in Average Return and rank 1 in Standard Deviation with the lowest value.

Table-9 : Ranking of the Schemes according to Average Return (AR) and Standard Deviation (SD)

Schemes	Direct Scheme		Regular Scheme	
	AR	SD	AR	SD
Aditya Birla Sunlife Small Cap Fund	13	10	13	12
Axis Small Cap Fund	05	01	09	01
DSP Small Cap Fund	10	07	08	08
Franklin India Smaller Companies Fund	12	03	12	04

(Contd...)

HDFC Small Cap Fund	08	06	06	06
ICICI Prudential Small Cap Fund	09	08	07	10
Kotak Small Cap Fund	04	04	04	07
L & T Emerging Business Fund	03	05	02	05
Nippon India Small Cap Fund	01	11	01	09
Quant Small Cap Fund	06	09	05	11
SBI Small Cap Fund	02	02	03	02
Sundaram Small Cap Fund	11	12	11	13
Union Small Cap Fund	07	13	10	03

Source : Compiled by the Author.

Table-10 shows the ranking of the scheme according to Sharpe, Treynor and Jensen Measures, where the scheme with the highest value is ranked 1 in all the measures.

Table-10 (a) : Ranking of the Schemes according to Sharpe, Treynor and Jensen Measures

Schemes	Direct Scheme		
	Sharpe	Treynor	Jenson
Aditya Birla Sunlife Small Cap Fund	13	13	13
Axis Small Cap Fund	01	01	01
DSP Small Cap Fund	09	10	10
Franklin India Smaller Companies Fund	10	11	11
HDFC Small Cap Fund	06	08	08
ICICI Prudential Small Cap Fund	08	09	09
Kotak Small Cap Fund	04	05	05
L & T Emerging Business Fund	05	07	06
Nippon India Small Cap Fund	03	04	02
Quant Small Cap Fund	07	03	04
SBI Small Cap Fund	02	02	03
Sundaram Small Cap Fund	12	12	12
Union Small Cap Fund	11	06	07

Source : Compiled by the Author.

Table-10 (b) : Ranking of the Schemes according to Sharpe, Treynor and Jenson Measures

Schemes	Regular Scheme		
	Sharpe	Treynor	Jenson
Aditya Birla Sunlife Small Cap Fund	13	13	13
Axis Small Cap Fund	05	04	06
DSP Small Cap Fund	09	10	10
Franklin India Smaller Companies Fund	11	11	11
HDFC Small Cap Fund	07	07	07
ICICI Prudential Small Cap Fund	08	08	08
Kotak Small Cap Fund	04	06	05
L & T Emerging Business Fund	03	05	04
Nippon India Small Cap Fund	01	03	01
Quant Small Cap Fund	06	01	03
SBI Small Cap Fund	02	02	02
Sundaram Small Cap Fund	12	12	12
Union Small Cap Fund	10	09	09

Source : Compiled by the Author.

Table-11 shows the Overall Performance Ranking of the mutual funds is evaluated under different methods in terms of S&P BSE Small cap Index, it cannot be expressed that a single scheme will outperform others under all methods. When some schemes perform better under some methods and some other schemes perform better under some other methods, selecting a single scheme as the best scheme will become difficult. To overcome this, the overall performance ranking of the schemes that include Average Return, Standard Deviation, Sharpe, Treynor and Jenson. Schemes are ranked according to their performance, as the scheme with highest value is given Rank 1, except in Standard Deviation. Finally, the scheme with the lowest average rank becomes the best scheme.

Table-11 : Overall Performance Ranking

Schemes	Overall Performance Ranking (Direct Scheme)	Overall Performance Ranking (Regular Scheme)
Aditya Birla Sunlife Small Cap Fund	13	13
Axis Small Cap Fund	01	03
DSP Small Cap Fund	11	11
Franklin India Smaller Ciompanies Fund	12	12
HDFC Small Cap Fund	07	07
ICICI Prudential Small Cap Fund	09	08
Kotak Small Cap Fund	03	04
L & T Emerging Business Fund	04	02
Nippon India Small Cap Fund	02	01
Quant Small Cap Fund	05	05
SBI Small Cap Fund	06	06
Sundaram Small Cap Fund	08	09
Union Small Cap Fund	10	10

Source : Compiled by the Author.

Conclusion

Out of the total thirteen schemes studied, ten schemes (direct category) and seven schemes (regular category) showed an average return higher than in comparison to the market return. **Nippon India Small Cap Fund** had shown the best average return whereas **Aditya Birla Sunlife Small Cap Fund** showed the worst performance in both direct and regular scheme. **Axis Small Cap Fund** was the least risky and **Union Small Cap Fund** was the riskiest fund in direct scheme and **Axis Small Cap Fund** was the least risky and **Sundaram Small Cap Fund** was the riskiest fund in regular scheme. Based on the overall performance ranking of the schemes it can be seen that **Axis Small Cap Fund** in Direct Scheme and **Nippon India Small Cap Fund** in Regular Scheme has shown the best performance and has outperformed in all the other schemes and the benchmark taken for the study.

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